

[DigiReady+] Workshop2: Data-driven Indicators of Digital Readiness in HEIs - Storyboard

Date: [add date]

[NOTE: Please adjust roles and times according to your setup]

Color coding:

- **Yellow** = Start of small group activities
- **Green** = Start of common activities

[Note] if the main group < 5 people then all activities can be carried out in common

START common session			
Agenda Item/Topic	Platform & Method	Prompt/Invitation and Content	Timing of Sequence & Materials (add links when there)
Welcome /Icebreaker 09:00 - 09:15 CET	Presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Remind the participants briefly the goal of the project and what was the discussions and outcomes of the previous workshop - Remind them you will be recording the session, or taking notes (if you're f2f) 	Materials: Slides, Agenda Total time: 15 min Parallel todos: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Post link to slides in Zoom (Researcher 2) <input type="checkbox"/> Record session, upload the recording and add link to schedule (Researcher 2)
Part 1 (Researcher 1) 09:15 - 10:00 CET	Discussion	<p>Data-driven Indicators of Digital Readiness in the wild and within the organization [45minutes]</p> <p>A. Introduce Digital Readiness Data-driven indicators from 4 frameworks and discuss how some of these could be applied within the organization</p> <p>B. Brainstorm other relevant indicators that could be used in context.</p>	Materials: Slides, Notes taking (Researcher 2) Total time: 45 min Special notes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involve each and every participant in the discussion

		<p>During the discussion bring up the whiteboard (or miro board) with the categories we identified in the previous workshop in order to help the discussion. The notes should be categorized in the following categories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Leadership, 2. Policies and Strategies, 3. Teaching and Learning Practices, 4. Training and Support, 5. Content and Curricula, 6. Infrastructure <p>Examples of measures to push the discussion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of online systems/platforms for technology-enhanced teaching and learning and statistics of usage - Number of online/hybrid/in person programs and courses - Number of students attending online/hybrid/in person programs and courses - E-assessment systems and statistics of usage - Learning outcomes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Starting with the highest rank/authority role, follow up with others - If one person dominates the discussion, try to put a full stop and involve others. For next discussion round, leave this person last <p>Note taking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -one note-taker takes notes on a whiteboard (virtual) or on post-its and sticks them on a board. - each time a note goes on the board, explicitly state that to your participants to make them aware of the existence of this note on the board. - the facilitator should direct the note taker, what notes to put on the note and under which category - on the side, keep observation notes that will NOT be visible to participants
<p>Break (15 minutes)</p> <p>10:00 - 10:15 CET</p>			
<p>Part 2-3 (Researcher 1)</p> <p>10:15 - 11:00 CET</p>	<p>Discussion</p>	<p>Data usage and potential issues from the use of university-collected data [45 minutes]</p> <p>Document information regarding data collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What kind of data does the organization collect? ● How are these data collected? (centrally, on predefined time periods, arbitrarily) <p>Discuss</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How could a data-driven tool be adopted by the organization? Who would have access to the results? Who can use the results and to what purpose? 	<p>Materials: Slides, Notes, Boards (same as before / use second part of the board)</p> <p>Total time: 45 min</p> <p>Special notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involve each and every participant in the discussion - Starting with the highest rank/authority role, follow up with others - If one person dominates the

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who owns the data that the tool would use? Who has access to the data? Who could use the data and under what circumstances? - Who would be responsible for setting up and maintaining a data-driven approach within the organization? 	discussion, try to put a full stop and involve others. For next discussion round, leave this person last
Break 16:00 - 16:15 CET			
START common session			
Agenda Item/Topic	Platform & Method	Prompt/Invitation and Content	Timing of Sequence & Materials
Part 3 (Researcher 1) 16:15 - 16:45	Open Knowledge Repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •IO3 introduction •Hands-on activity 	Materials: Slides, participants' notes Total time: 30 min <input type="checkbox"/> Record session, upload recording and add link to schedule (Researcher 2)
Wrap-up (Researcher 1) 11:00 - 11:15 CET	Outro presentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Summarize main points of previous discussions •Point out we will follow up with a report on the activity 3 weeks after the workshop. -Remind them that there will be a multiplier event following up and they will receive invitations THANK PARTICIPANTS!	Materials: Slides Total Time: 15 min
END OF WORKSHOP			